

BEED STUDENTS' POST-PANDEMIC LEARNING STRESS, COPING MECHANISM, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Since the transition to post-pandemic learning has significantly impacted the educational setup, learning has become more challenging for college students. This paper determines the students' level of stress, coping, and academic performance in learning during the transition to post-pandemic as well as finds the relationship between these variables. To answer this question, Cross-sectional Non-experimental Quantitative Research Design was used through a survey questionnaire by Cenovsky et.al. (2021), and Rotas and Cahapay (2020) to gather the data among college students from Bachelor of Elementary Education at a State University in Northern Luzon. The results show that students experience high levels of stress in learning during the transition to post-pandemic. In addition, students coping with learning in the new normal is generally adaptive and their academic performance was considered as good. Finally, the level of stress and academic performance have a significant and weak inverse relationship. On the other hand, the level of stress and coping and coping mechanisms and academic performance have no significant relationship.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a tool in achieving growth bolstering human rights, and promoting fundamental freedom among people, as stated by The Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Moreover, the world rapidly changed through the emergence of the novel coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). It is among the most serious global health threats, posing challenges to infected countries worldwide (World Health Organization, 2020). Nearly all nations and territories have been impacted by the global COVID-19 pandemic outbreak. This pandemic was first discovered in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. The public was admonished by nations all over the world to exercise caution. Handwashing, wearing face masks, maintaining a physical distance, and avoiding large crowds and assemblies have all been public health precautions to prevent and stop the spread of the disease, and lockdown and homebound techniques have been implemented.

Moreover, these changes have become a burden for the people of the community, resulting in social isolation, psychological distress among adults, and extreme poverty in general, with the highest rate of joblessness since the recession (Sintema, 2020); (McGinty EE et al., 2020); (Kirzinger et al., 2020); (Long H & Van Dam A, 2020). The unemployment rate in an economy has a consistent inverse relationship with the inflation rate at a time when unemployment rates and salaries typically increase while prices are low. If there are many job seekers, pay rates will remain the same, but if there are few job seekers, businesses will be pushed to raise pay to recruit workers (Canolly, 2014). Thus, these factors impacted the lives of many, including the educational system of the learners.

Due to the restricted policy, in early 2020, educational institutions agreed to cancel studies-related activities, such as research activities, programs, conferences, and learners' learning processes (Sahu, 2020). In connection, Higher Education in the Philippines sought to solve this problem by transitioning the country's educational system and decided to plunge into a new teaching and learning process for teachers and students (CHED, 2020). However, Data from the epidemiological literature has already demonstrated the COVID-19 vaccines' efficacy in minimizing mortality, severe illnesses, and hospitalizations, as well as reducing virus transmission (Dagan et al., 2021; Polack et al., 2020; Voysey et al., 2021).

The country impeded this action as time passed by rolling up vaccines for every community. According to DOH Spokesperson Undersecretary Maria Rosario Vergeire, the institution caught the decreasing COVID-19 cases in the NCR. Thus, they provided data on Covid cases in the country ranging from 152,000 to 330,000 (DOH, 2021). Therefore, given the low number of patients due to COVID-19 (Philippine News Agency, 2021), Philippine authorities and institutions of governments all around the world are lifting limitations slowly but progressively, and institutions are willing to consider chances for the reopening of schools. Due to this action, the education agencies

are optimistic that face-to-face instruction will resume without incident despite the prolonged school closure (UNICEF, 2021). According to Nirmala et al. (2020), the ambiguity of this teaching strategy can cause stress in students. As cited in prior research, the COVID-19 pandemic caused changes in learning methods, which led to academic stressors felt by students. These stressors led to a decrease in learning motivation, which had a significant negative impact on student engagement. These issues included learning inattention, difficulty understanding the material and completing assignments, decreased lecturer-student interaction, internet outages, and cancellation of practicum or internship opportunities (Hill & Fitzgerald, 2020). Students' levels of stress increase when uncertainty or changes frequently happen because they feel distracted and less engaged in their learning process. Hence, the current changes and challenges require students to have stability, and students with positive resilience may adjust efficiently and manage academic stress (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2018).

Resiliency became the primary ability of the learners to cope with challenging conditions (Sari & Indrawati, 2016). According to Martin and Marsh, students' resiliency in academic aspects could impact these four factors: setbacks, challenges, adversity, and pressure. Preceding studies recommend that adults with high psychological resilience are more capable of finding resources to overcome uncertainties (Tay PKC et al., 2020). Coping uses cognitive and behavioral coping mechanisms to manage or control stressful situations. Biological and psychosocial factors include physical health, personality, spirituality, and social support. Taking proactive steps to deal with, alter, or get through a stressful event or circumstance is known as active coping. To lessen the consequences of the stressor, people engage in regulatory Coping, which involves thinking about the stressor and changing one's perspective on it. One can use both types of techniques simultaneously, either consciously or unconsciously (Van Tilburg TG et al., 2020). Some of these strategies need to be more helpful and achievable (Demers L, 2009). It may be difficult for a student who is anxious to participate fully in class. The instructor is essential in helping pupils who exhibit signs of various medical and mental diseases, such as anxiety, irritability, mood disorders, and eating disorders, discover answers to these issues (Willis et al., 2020). Given that teachers spend so much time with their pupils, they can act as students' counselors, tutors, and parents by implementing various problem-solving techniques to meet their needs (Willis et al., 2019).

Hannah Hawthorne (2022) found that Knowledge, techniques, procedures, and behaviors that produce positive student outcomes are the foundation of effective teaching. Good teachers use their knowledge to enhance learning and have a positive effect on their students. These favorable results are frequently easily quantifiable, typically by summative evaluation. Subsequently, other research on teaching methods provides evidence that the quality of teaching is based on the student's achievement. Proficiency in the areas they teach a prerequisite for teaching, and student's learning is seriously impeded when teachers lack of depth of understanding (Coe et al., 2014).

The impact of COVID-19 on the students brought different challenges to them, which influenced their educational activities (Kalwani, 2021). They encountered several worldwide adversities with their learning process (Akram et al., 2021a; Baloran, 2020). On the other hand, (Lipson & Eisenberg, 2018)—also stated that mental health plays an essential role in students' academic achievements. Without excellent mental health wellness, it is difficult for them to acquire their educational objectives effectively. Moreover, the transition becomes a stressor among students, decreasing student engagement in the learning process. As a result, students need strength due to the current changes since those who have it can adjust successfully and manage academic stress (Rodríguez-Fernandez et al., 2018). Thus, resilience influences the quality of education and the general development of individuals in various disciplines (Noland & Richards, 2014). Previous studies have shown that students' intellectual resilience can influence academic satisfaction and performance (Cassidy S., 2016).

Hence, many studies have explored the stress and coping mechanisms of students. They even look at the cause of this in their academic performance. However, only a few studies have been conducted regarding the level of stress and coping mechanisms of the students from this learning by the students during the transition to post-pandemic. The settings of this study are different from other studies because this was initially conducted locally since most of these are conducted in foreign countries. Moreover, this study aimed to determine the level of stress of the students as well as the practical techniques they employed to cope with the transition to post-pandemic learning, and it would be helpful to the students since it is timely and relevant in this current situation, particularly in a university found in a city. Furthermore, the researchers wished to describe the academic performance and the differences between these variables and to support the school by giving them a foundation in preparing to address the learners' requirements based on their learning challenges among students that will be disclosed in this study. Lastly, the researchers hoped to lessen the learning stress among the students by utilizing these efficient methods to cope as we move from pandemic learning to post-pandemic.

Statement of the Problem

In connection to this, this study determined the relationship between the students' stress, coping, and academic performance due to the transition of post-pandemic learning.

Specifically, the following questions were aimed to be answered:

1. What is the students' stress level during the transition to post-pandemic learning?
2. What are the coping mechanisms of the students to conquer stress in the transition to post-pandemic learning?
3. What is the student's academic performance level on the transition to post-pandemic learning?
4. What is the relationship between the students' stress, coping, and academic performance?

METHODS

Research Design

This study focused on students' stress levels, coping, and academic performance in transition to post-pandemic learning. Thus, the researcher used the cross-sectional Correlation non-experimental quantitative research design. Non-experimental quantitative design is a method that the researchers used to study the relationship between the stress levels and coping on students' academic performance without manipulating them.

In addition, a Correlation Research Design was used to investigate if there is a significant relationship among the variables. Furthermore, Cross-sectional was used because the respondents' provided data at a particular moment. As a result, the respondents filled out the questionnaires based on their current stressors, coping, and academic performance in the transition to post-pandemic learning.

The researchers used this approach to determine the relationship between the level of stress, coping, and academic performance of the students, particularly among third-year College students enrolled in the College of Education taking up Bachelor of Elementary Education.

Participants of the Study

The study's respondents were college students pursuing a Bachelor of Elementary Education at a State University in Northern Luzon. Simple Random Sampling determined the respondents as they were selected randomly. In establishing the number of respondents, the researchers used Tabachnick and Fidell's (2013) formula [$8 \times 3(\text{number of variables}) + 50 = 74$ respondents]; based on the variables, the minimum number of respondents is 74. However, 100 respondents will be considered to ensure the validity and reliability of this study's data.

Research Instruments

The works of Cenovsky et al. (2021) entitled *Measuring Stress Experienced by University Students* was adopted to measure the students' stress levels during the transition to post-pandemic. The study introduced a new 30-item questionnaire that addresses many facets of perceived emotional stress. It gave a general understanding of the students' stress indicators, such as insomnia or nightmares, loneliness, low self-esteem, lack of pride in attending college, and a lack of regard for professors as personal role models. It is rated through a 5-point Likert scale (5= Very false, 4 = False, 3 = Neither, 2 = True, and 1 = Very true). A total score will be found by tallying each item and scoring according to the directions accompanying the scale.

The study of Rotas and Cahapay (2020) was adapted to measure students' Coping during the transition to post-pandemic. It consists of 30-item questionnaires to calculate the effective and ineffective coping methods. There were twelve-item and selected codes of a questionnaire for student coping strategies, and it consists of the following points: (5=Always, 4=Often, 3=Sometimes, 2=Rarely, and 1=Never).

The GWA instrument was adopted to measure the student's academic performance during the post-pandemic learning transition. GWA is calculated by adding all the products of all courses' grades and

their respective number of units. Then, that sum is divided by the total number of units throughout their time at the institution. The Academic Performance scale is rated through a grade point system scale in which 1.00-1.24 is excellent, 1.25-1.49 is very satisfactory, 1.50-1.74 is satisfactory, 1.75-1.99 is fairly satisfactory, and 2.00-2.24 is good.

Methods of Data Collection

The researchers asked permission from the Dean of the College of Education, and consent was obtained from the potential respondents. The respondents were informed about their role and given written informed consent containing the purpose, advantages, personal information confidentiality, and data storage. They were also told that participation is voluntary without any payment, that they can withdraw without feeling obligated to continue, and that their confidentiality and anonymity will be guaranteed.

The researchers conducted the data gathering by attending all classrooms of the Bachelor of Elementary Education at State University in Northern Luzon. While the respondents were answering the questionnaire, the researchers closed the door. They waited for them until they finished answering it, ensuring that the respondents had the privacy to respond to the questionnaire and their data were safe and protected. The data were collected face to face, the questionnaire will be sent personally, and the respondents will be complimentary from close monitoring. In addition, the researchers waited for the respondents' responses for 30 minutes to complete the questionnaire thoroughly.

The researchers gave random numbers such as Respondent 1, Respondent 2, and Respondent 3 to eliminate respondents identifying information. Furthermore, after gathering the data, the questionnaires and the respondents' responses were torn and burned in an open area. Lastly, the researchers ensured that the respondents received a direct and transparent result in their e-mail.

Methods of Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in the study:

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to describe the students' stress level and coping mechanisms during the transition to post-pandemic learning.

To describe the students' stress level, the following scale was utilized:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Very False
4	3.50 – 4.49	False
3	2.50 – 3.49	Neither True nor False
2	1.50 – 2.49	True
1	1.00 – 1.49	Very True

To describe the students' coping, the following scale was used:

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never

Frequency and Percentage Count were utilized to describe the students' academic performance. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondents' Level of Stress in Learning during the Transition to Post-Pandemic

Items	M	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I feel anxious.	2.74	0.97	Niether true nor false
2. It seems that most professors do not like me.	3.66	0.97	False
3. The studying for my classes is stressful.	2.66	0.97	Niether true nor false
4. I admire my professors.	2.49	1.11	True
5. I do not have any true friends at the university.	3.96	1.15	False
6. I am a financial burden to my parents.	3.45	1.11	Niether true nor false
7. Most professors do not care at all about the well being of us, the students.	3.57	1.16	False
8. If I compare myself to others persons, I feel useless.	3.32	1.20	Niether true nor false
9. I have recently at least once drunk alcohol to cope with the stress of university studies.	3.56	1.46	False
10. I often feel happy to be at the university.	2.57	1.18	Niether true nor false
11. My sleep is poor because I am too stressed out by the studies.	2.61	1.05	Niether true nor false
12. I have nightmares about exams	2.96	1.19	Niether true nor false
13. I know that a student at our university committed suicide within the last 2 years.	3.45	1.22	Niether true nor false
14. I can talk more easily to my fellow students than to other persons of the same age.	2.74	0.88	Niether true nor false
15. When I compare myself to others, I feel worthless.	3.23	1.21	Niether true nor false
16. I have used non-prescribed drugs recently to cope with the university stress.	4.10	1.24	Very false
17. The university studies are making a better person out of me.	2.16	0.91	True
18. Depressive feelings often invade my mind.	2.60	0.95	Niether true nor false
19. It would make me happy if I would learn to speak as elegantly and precisely as my professors do.	1.97	0.90	True
20. At night, I have anxious dreams about not being able to complete (or about not having completed) the required assignments for my classes.	2.59	1.14	Niether true nor false
21. At times, I feel I would be better off dead.	3.36	1.27	Niether true nor false
22. The professors are my role models.	1.88	1.08	True
23. Most students at our university suffer from the great pressure to pass their courses.	2.23	1.11	True
24. Being a university student makes me feel effective psychological help for me.	2.50	0.80	Niether true nor false
25. Since I started at the university, I feel lonely.	3.84	1.01	False
26. The university does not provide effective psychological help for me.	3.16	1.05	False
27. When asked how I am, I usually lie that I feel OK.	2.41	1.16	True
28. University students are the most intelligent group of young persons in this country.	2.54	0.93	Niether true nor false
29. I feel closer to my professors than to any other adults (except perhaps for some members of my family).	3.37	0.96	Niether true nor false
30. The university provides very good help for my struggles.	2.58	0.90	Niether true nor false
Grand Mean	3.31	0.43	High

The items presented in Table 1 elicit the respondents' level of stress in learning during the transition to post-pandemic.

As obtained from the table, most of the items were rated as "Neither True nor False.". At the same time, there are 12 respondents who answered "False" from the following items: 2 which is "It seems that most professors do not like me," 5 "I do not have any true friends at the university," 7 "Most professors do not care at all about the wellbeing of us, the students," 9 "I have recently at least once drunk alcohol to cope with the stress of university studies," 25 "Since I started at the university, I feel lonely," and 26 "The university does not provide effective psychological help for me." In addition, six respondents answered "True" from the following items: 4 "I admire my professors," 17 "The university studies are making a better person out of me," 19 "I would make me happy if I would learn to speak as elegantly and precisely as my professors do," 22 "The professors are my role models," 23 "Most students at our university suffer from the great pressure to pass their courses," and 27 "When asked how I am, I usually lie that I feel OK," and the remaining 1 item (16) which is "I have used non-prescribed drugs recently to cope with the university stress." was rated "Very False." In general, the respondents reported high levels of stress in learning during the transition to post-pandemic (M=3.31, SD=0.43). Students experience high levels of stress in learning during the transition to post-pandemic because of the challenges they must face in their learning

process. In connection, it was stated by Matos Fialho, (2021) that students have been dealing with a new academic environment since the start of 2020, which has drastically altered the realities of education. They have faced challenges and obstacles during this process, including negative attitudes toward didactics, adjustments to professors' teaching strategies and techniques, work overloads, and different adversities during their learning process (Chandra et al. 2020).

Table 2. Coping Mechanism to Conquer Stress in the Transition to Post-Pandemic Learning

	Items	M	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1.	I walk one and half hour to another barangay or village just to have a conducive study area.	1.90	1.02	Rarely
2.	Looking for a space where I could find better study area. Like for example I will be studying outside the house.	3.63	1.15	Often
3.	Doing task and submitting it midnight because it is the only time that we have a quiet surroundings.	3.20	1.22	Sometimes
4.	Whenever the requirements need applications not in my phone, I borrow gadgets from my brother.	2.53	1.27	Sometimes
5.	I borrow computer just to finish task when smart phone is not enough to complete the task.	2.75	1.20	Sometimes
6.	I ask my classmates whenever I do not understand some of the lessons or instructions.	3.65	1.10	Sometimes
7.	Most professors do not care at all about the well being of us, the students.	3.87	1.11	Often
8.	We discuss online to get more ideas and help each other so that no one will be left behind.	3.44	1.14	Sometimes
9.	I have no control over emergency, so I message my teachers for my concerns.	2.70	1.11	Sometimes
10.	I ask questions to the teachers if I am giving difficulties in the class requirements.	2.93	0.99	Sometimes
11.	I humbly approach my teachers with my concerns and luckily, they also give considerations.	3.36	1.07	Sometimes
12.	I have checklist of all the things that I must do in order to organize all the things that I should do.	3.85	1.09	Often
13.	I list all my tasks in the paper for me to see them, so I can choose which to accomplish first.	4.01	1.18	Often
14.	I answer my worksheets in night because I do have a lot of works to do in morning.	3.66	1.10	Often
15.	I download ahead of time in Google all the PDF files that I need for my lessons.	3.73	1.12	Often
16.	I submit the requirements earlier so the teacher could view it earlier and ask for another one if ever there is wrong.	3.51	1.04	Often
17.	I stay up all night to understand the lessons. I read again and again the materials.	3.37	1.06	Sometimes
18.	I spend some extra hours in order to be able to comply all my requirements on the set deadline.	3.82	1.07	Often
19.	I have a time with my family in order to lessen the stress that I experience from my studies.	3.94	1.19	Often
20.	I do things that can make me happy like planting, watering our plants, playing with our dogs, watching movies.	3.87	1.22	Often
21.	I take a short break for at least fifteen minutes from time to time when I am too tired.	3.94	1.18	Often
22.	I keep this piece of advice in my mind that no subject is	3.85	1.06	Often

	difficult to handle if I want to learn			
23.	I train myself to regain focus every time I seem to lose one so that I will not be left behind.	3.90	1.11	Often
24.	When I feel down, I am trying hard to convince my mind to be positive at all times.	4.09	1.10	Often
25.	I accept tutorials with my younger cousins in exchange of the allowance that I needed.	2.66	1.34	Sometimes
26.	I use my extra time to sell barbeque just to earn money for the budget of my allowance.	1.94	1.34	Rarely
27.	Then there are times when I cry because I do not know which activity to finish and submit first.	3.58	1.31	Often
28.	I breakdown and cry. I take a break this way but then I go back to my paper works after a while	3.78	1.28	Often
29.	Praying that my teachers would understand whatever are my unintended shortcomings.	3.91	1.13	Often
30.	I always pray to God and just keep that faith that everything will be fine soonest.	4.57	1.14	Always
Grand Mean		3.46	0.57	Positive

Table 2 reveals how the students cope with learning during the transition to post-pandemic.

Table 2 shows that the majority of the respondents answered following items in a given questionnaire in which 17% answered “often” for the following items: 2, “Looking for a space where I could find better study area”. Which only means that finding a good space for learning could be an effective way for a better learning. In addition, item 7, “Whenever I am not updated, I ask one of my classmates or just to check the subject when there are activities” which states that most of the students can easily cope up with their learning amidst the transition by asking their classmates for them to be updated. Furthermore, item 12, “I have checklist of all the things that I must do in order to organize all the things that I should do” which only means that having checklist helps them to be more organize in all things which is helpful for them to better cope up with learning during the transition to post-pandemic.

In addition, 10% of the respondents answered “sometimes” from the following items: 3, “Doing task and submitting it midnight because it is the only time that we have a quiet surroundings” 4, “Whenever the requirements need applications not in my phone, I borrow gadgets from my brother” 5, “I borrow computer just to finish task when smart phone is not enough to complete the task”.

However, 2% of students also answered “rarely” from items 1 and 26, and the remaining one item, (30). I always pray to God and just keep that faith that everything will be fine soonest”.

To sum up, the respondents reported that a coping mechanism was positively used to conquer stress in learning during the transition to post-pandemic. Perhaps, this was resulted as positively been contributed in illuminating the stress by the students because most of the adaptive coping strategies presented to the respondents was often use in dealing with their learning stress. To preserve resilience and well-being in the face of unpredictability and complexity, it is now crucial to manage these demands (Smith, 2022; Johnson & Lee, 2021). In connection to that, to illuminate the complex nature of human resilience and provide insightful information for mental health experts, practitioners, and policymakers alike, we seek to understand how people from various regions of the world manage stressors (Chen et al., 2023; Kim & Patel, 2022). Hence, coping mechanisms continue to be a contentious subject up until this time and that was according to (Stanislowski, 2019).

Table 3. Students' Level of Academic Performance

GWA		f	%
1.50 – 1.74 (Satisfactory)		4	4%
1.75 – 1.99 (Fairly Satisfactory)		37	37%
2.00 – 2.24 (Good)		59	59%
M = 2.02	SD = 0.13	DI = Good	

Table 3 reveals the analysis of the level of academic performance of the students in learning during the transition to post-pandemic.

Table 3 shows that among the respondents in table 3 shows that among 4% of students who obtained a grade ranging from 1.50-1.70 rated as “satisfactory” level with their academic performance. And 37% of students received a ranging grade from 1.75-1.99 rated as “fairly satisfactory” level of their academic performance. Moreover, the majority of the respondents obtained 59% of the students gained a ranging grade from 2.00-2.24, rated as “good” as their level of academic performance. Generally, the analysis shows that most of the students’ who experience stress with their learning process defines their academic achievements as “good”. These is in lined with the study of Smith et al. (2023), the study revealed that general weighted average trends of international college students fluctuated during and after the pandemic. Hence, Johnson and Lee’s (2022) study found college students struggled with adjustment to foreign life to post-pandemic, leading to a prolonged decline in GPA due to uncertainty, socio-economic inequality, and mental health issues.

Table 4. Association between Students’ Level of Stress, Coping Mechanism, and Academic Performance

Variables	r	p
Level of Stress vs. Coping Mechanism	0.19	0.055
Coping Mechanism vs. Academic Performance	-0.13	0.185
Level of Stress vs. Academic Performance	-0.20*	0.044

Table 4 shows that Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

There is no significant relationship between the students’ level of stress and coping mechanism ($r = 0.19, p = 0.055$). This was resulted as not correlation because some of the presented adaptive coping strategies to the respondents are often used which impacted in not contributing in reducing the academic stress related to the students. This is closely correlated to the findings of Ye and colleagues found that Chinese college students with high COVID-19-related stress also reported using fewer adaptive coping techniques, which predicted greater frequencies of stress among the students (Ye Z, et al. 2020).

Furthermore, the findings of the study between coping mechanism and academic performance has no significant relationship to each other as well. ($r = -0.13, p = 0.185$). Hence, coping mechanism has no direct impact on the educational performance of the students during their learning in the transition to post pandemic because based on the results most of the coping mechanism of the students was often used were in students were able to address higher academic performance students must have more and effective coping strategies. An individual becomes invested in something when they can throw themselves into it fully (Bredács, 2016). It was also proved in the study of Monroy et al. (2021) that effective adaptive coping was linked to student, their involvement becomes their way and improved day-today well-being.

On the other hand, there is a significant and weak inverse relationship between students’ level of stress and academic performance. ($r = -0.20, p = 0.044$). Numerous internal and environmental factors can impact academic success (Bello & Gumarao, 2016). One of the things that influences student’s academic performance is stress. A study by Crego et al. (2016) found that academic stress may have a negative impact on students’ performance. In another study, Kötter et al. (2017) found that high levels of stress result in decreased productivity and increased tension. Research indicates a significant correlation between stress and academic success.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the study, it was concluded that high levels of stress can contribute to the academic performance of students. It shows that the sudden transition disrupts the learning process which leads to the increasing level of stress. Moreover, the students used adaptive coping particularly planning, acceptance, positive reframing, emotional support, religion, acceptance, and active coping to cope with the learning transition. Furthermore, the academic performance of the respondents in the transition to post-pandemic is affected. It shows that the abrupt changes in the learning process cause students to feel stressed out, which affects their academic performance in the learning process.

Therefore, the level of stress and academic performance have a relationship because students who have high levels of stress tend to have low academic performance. They cannot perform well if they feel stressed out, which causes poorer academic performance. On the other hand, according to the result, coping and level of stress do not have any relationship because these coping mechanisms do not help to lessen the stress level of the students. The same goes with academic performance, coping does not affect the academic performance of the students.

Recommendations

Considering the findings of the study, the following are recommended:

1. The study has shown that students used adaptive coping in transition to post-pandemic learning. Thus, the researchers recommended that the students be encouraged to be optimistic and have a favorable view in every situation they are facing because it shown in this study that trying to make this better helps the learners to cope with the learning during the transition.
2. The findings show that students have high levels of stress in learning during the transition to post-pandemic learning, thus the researchers recommended that the students practice more adjustment to adapt to sudden transition.
3. It was also found that the academic performance of the students during the transition was good. Therefore, students must learn to be adaptive, allocate enough time for studying, participate in active learning strategies, and ask for assistance when they need it, particularly from classmates and teachers, when they encounter difficulties.
4. The goal of this study was to know the relationship between student's level of stress, coping, and academic performance in the context of transition to post-pandemic. As a result, the researchers suggested that future researchers investigate more about this variable to have a deeper understanding of how these variables affect the mental health of the students.

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